

JURISPRUDENCE

MALTA FROM A LEGAL POINT OF VIEW (Malta as a good example for Georgia)

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Abstract

Today it is very important to raise public awareness of the European Union and its member States. This paper focuses on Malta, the smallest EU country, its history, constitutional foundations, and forms of governance. Prospects for Georgia's relations with the Republic of Malta are also discussed.

Keywords: Malta, Constitution, Government system, Peculiarities of Constitutional Law

Instead of an introduction

Today, Georgia's achievements in rapprochement with the European Union have become increasingly visible, and the issue of raising public awareness of the European Union and the countries of the European Union takes a considerable place in Georgia's educational space. As a lawyer and a representative of the field of education, I consider it expedient to pay special attention to teaching European (constitutional/state law) law at universities; It is important to hold public lectures and special master classes in this field. In our university, all conditions are created in this regard, which has affected the level of vocational and civic education of students.

In my proposed scientific paper this time, I focus on the constitutional foundations and governance forms of the smallest country in the European Union, Malta.

From the history of Malta

Before touching upon the constitution of Malta, let me briefly review some important details concerning Malta. The official name of Malta is the Republic of Malta. Malta, Repubblika ta' Malta (Maltese), Republic of Malta. There are several options for explaining the name: The most appropriate is the Phoenician variant, Malat, which means harbor, and the Greek variant; "Meli" - honey and "Malta" - bee (Maltese honey is well known). /See reference list 3/. The capital of Malta is Valletta, state languages: are Maltese, and English. The currency is the euro. Malta consists of three islands: Malta Island, Gozo, and Comino. Many temples have been found in Malta that are older than the Egyptian pyramids. The Maltese consider the Knights to be the best years in their history, since then their fleet has been ruled by the Mediterranean. Over the centuries Malta has experienced invasions by the Phoenicians, the Greeks, the Romans, and the Arabs. It became a British colony in 1814 and has been an independent state since 1964, which we will discuss in more detail below. A referendum on the islands was held in May 2003 and a majority of the population supported the EU. The country has been a member of the European Union since 2004. Malta emerged as a State as early as 6,000 years ago. Today it is a small country, a real open-air museum. Compared to the number of historical monuments and museums the country is only inferior to Rome.

The Carthaginians, Phoenicians, Arabs, and Normans, the Knights of the Order of St. John and Napoleon. /See reference list 1/. left their mark on Malta. World civilizations were coming and going, and Malta remained.

Constitutional Development of Malta

Now let's touch upon directly at the constitutional development of the smallest EU member state. The current constitution of Malta is the result of a long historical development. Elements of statehood, democracy, rule of law, and protection of human rights and freedoms took various forms in the early 19th century when French domination (since 1789) was replaced by British domination (1800 years) and step by step following the recognition of human rights and freedom. In this connection, the population was given the right to participate in local government and then self-government elections, with some restrictions and, of course, under British control.

The first constitution appeared in Malta as early as the late 19th century. In 1887 the constitution recognized the supreme authority of the British monarch. The monarch had a representative in Malta as a governor. According to the constitution of 1921 in the process of management of internal affairs, the executive branch was obliged responsibility before the parliament. After World War II, all over the world, the process of self-determination and separation into independent states intensified again, which also concerned Malta. The new 1947 constitution of Malta is a clear expression of this, despite growing rights in British governance, defense, civil aviation, money circulation, and the monetary and credit system of the country, in matters of citizenship the rights of the Maltese were increasing. Starting from this period, the legislative body (40 members at the time) was elected on a proportional basis, and the struggle for full independence intensified. A special constitutional commission appointed by the British authorities was tasked with drafting a new constitution. The new constitution came into force in 1961. The influence of the British authorities was further narrowed, and The Parliament gained unlimited legislative power. Britain has found it most difficult to adapt to Malta's growing authority in international affairs and defense. In 1921, Malta officially applied to London and sought recognition as an independent state within the British Commonwealth.

The issues raised at the General Conference and the referendum in Malta accelerated the UK's adoption of the law in 1964. Malta was recognized as an independent State and became a Member of the United Nations. On the one hand, Malta was headed by a British monarch, whose constitutional monarchy was led by the Governor-General in the country, and on the other hand, many constitutional rights, including the right to vote, were recognized (From the age of 21, for those who have lived in Malta for at least 2 years). The status and functions of the Parliament as a representative body, the Prime Minister's position in the governance of the country much more have been further strengthened, etc.

The Constitution of Malta consists of 11 chapters and 124 articles. The first chapter deals with the state system, symbols, and other important attributes, the role of the Constitution as the supreme law. The second chapter is devoted to the basic principles of social protection. It is no coincidence that the citizenship issues have been allocated as a separate chapter (Chapter 3), which in our opinion should be considered (This is a very important and principled issue for Maltese people, it is difficult to obtain citizenship, acquire real estate (especially to buy land) and conduct business for non-citizens here). Chapter 4 deals with basic human rights and freedoms. Chapter 5 is devoted to the Institute of the President, Chapter 6 touches upon Parliament's Power, Chapter 7 is connected with Government, Chapter 8 is related to Judicial Power, and Chapter 9 concerns Economic Policy and Financial Issues. Chapter 10 is separately dedicated to the state, a public service that is not typical for most constitutions of European countries today, which we consider a noteworthy and interesting fact. Chapter 11 contains provisions which, according to the authors of the Constitution, do not fit into the above chapters in terms of their content, but depending on state importance it was necessary their allocation by separate chapters. The last chapter covers constitutional laws, treaties, and some issues which are related to the British community. /See reference list 2/.

Several changes were made in the Constitution in 1964-1974 (According to the Article 66 of the Constitution, requires the approval of 2/3 of the MPs.). Among them, the term "Citizen of the British Commonwealth" (1965, 1967) was introduced into the Constitution about freedom of speech (1966). A major adjustment was made in 1974 when Malta remained in the British Commonwealth (Malta, as an independent republic, already had its president and was no longer subject to the British Queen).

Interdependence of the various government branches in Malta

As it is known the state system is very similar to the British model. Malta is a parliamentary republic. The main political figure is the Prime Minister, the election-winning party's leader. The President exercises executive power (Malta, as an independent republic, already had its president and was no longer subject to the British Queen).

He is the highest representative of the country in the international arena (A. 78 - The Constitution of

Malta). The President is the main guarantee of the Constitution, he appoints judges, has the right to pardon, etc. /A. 93 - The Constitution of Malta/. The President is elected by the Parliament for a five-year term.

The Prime Minister and ministers are responsible to Parliament, which can be dissolved by the President, that is, the Prime Minister (from the deputies representing the party that has won the parliamentary elections, on the proposal of the Prime Minister). The Prime Minister is considered the head of government (The Prime Minister is obliged to inform the President periodically on specific issues related to current events in the country and the implementation of executive power).

I would like to draw your attention to a very important provision of the Constitution; Malta officially has an institution of opposition leaders. In this post, the president appoints the leader of the largest opposition party. /A. 90 - The Constitution of Malta/.

The peculiarities of the legislative power

The Parliament of Malta is unicameral, it consists of the House of Representatives (minimum – 65, maximum - 69 MPs). (This depends on the number of voters, which is very important for a well-managed electoral system); The decision shall be taken by majority vote. However, if the votes are split, the decisive vote belongs to the chairman. As mentioned above, the President can dissolve Parliament. He can also temporarily suspend the Parliament's activity. If the Parliament declares no confidence in the Government, the President may dissolve one or the other. The dismissal of Parliament may be the absence of candidates for the post of Prime Minister. The president may not dismiss the government based on the Prime Minister's recommendation (if the President considers that this step will harm the State).

Local councils

Although Malta is a unitary state, local councils operate in its territory. /A. 115 - The Constitution of Malta/. Their number is not deliberately specified. This is because, as the constitutionalists point out, their number increases or decreases as a result of the state's need. /See reference list 2/. The Council shall be elected for a term of three years by a proportional system. The Council exercises its powers within a specific territory. The Chairman of the Council shall be considered as the Mayor elected by the Council members.

Malta and nationalism, rigorous policies toward foreigners

The indigenous population of Malta is not diverse and in every way tries to preserve its old look and identity. Sometimes it even becomes too rigorous. The national, ethnic issue is always the most expressed towards Malta. However, after the country joined the EU, the situation was more or less settled, and years-old confrontations between the Nationals (National Movement of Malta) and the Labor Party over Malta's foreign course and development have been stopped. /See reference list 4/. In Malta, you will no longer see a poor population. At the same time, the European Council of

the European Union periodically reproaches the Maltese authorities for their rigid policy towards foreigners. The UN also criticizes Malta's refugee policy because of its chosen clear position on refugees. The largest amount of foreign nationals or stateless persons who illegally cross Malta's borders come from North Africa. Most EU member states are known to be NATO members at the same time. In Malta, the case is different. Malta's Constitution states that it is a neutral state that strives for a peaceful world order, and has the ability to defend itself, but will never join any military-political organization. As it is known, most EU member states are NATO members at the same time. In Malta, the case is different. There is a record in Malta's Constitution that it is a neutral state that seeks a peaceful world order and is capable of protecting itself but will never join any military-political organization. Therefore, no country on the territory of Malta can locate military bases; the only exception is the decision of the UN Security Council to maintain peace in the region.

Malta - Religion Role

Catholicism is recognized as a state religion, but respect and tolerance for other religions are reinforced in Chapter 4 of the Constitution. The parish of the Catholic Church is 98 percent. Atheists are not found among the local population. Malta has many churches and monasteries. Malta has the largest number of temples (on a worldwide scale); /See reference list 5/. There are many monasteries of nuns and monks. In some places, the lifestyle is so harsh that many can't stand it all. In every school, religion is a compulsory educational discipline. I think that drawing parallels with Georgia is more important here, Georgia is a multiethnic and multicultural country, so it is difficult to say, for example, how much in our country will justify itself with the same attitude towards the Orthodox Christian religion. Though the special role recognized by the Constitution towards the Georgian Church should find a more positive expression in today's public life, would probably be better and more useful to the community.

Prospects of cooperation

In this part of the article I would like to draw your attention to the forms and prospects of cooperation between Georgia and Malta. I also highlight the interest of Grigol Robakidze University in this area.

The main areas of cooperation are:

Agreements with the Republic of Malta include cooperation in the following areas: avoiding double taxation of income and capital, tax evasion, cooperation in the fight against crime, culture, science, and education. Bilateral relations between the two countries are characterized by positive dynamics; visits are carried out at both the executive and legislative levels. Within the framework of cooperation with the Mediterranean Academy of Diplomatic Studies of the University of Malta, a program is being implemented that allows Georgian diplomats and government officials to undergo advanced training at the Diplomatic Academy of Malta, as we see in the fields of cultural and educational, anti-crime and other fields between Malta and

Georgia is getting stronger. Frequent meetings of representatives of business and tourism, and planning of direct flights to Tbilisi-Malta are not accidental. For Georgia it is important to protect values such as centuries-old national traditions, language, religious beliefs, and problems of cultural identity, it is certainly important to study/analyze the path achieved by Malta with the purpose of rapprochement with the European Union. That is why Grigol Robakidze University attaches special importance to cooperation with the Georgian Culture Center in Malta and signing a memorandum in the future, which involves introducing students to European culture and history to bring them closer to the institutions of the European Union, to implement joint educational projects. All this will undoubtedly contribute to the European integration of Georgia.

Finally, the reader would be interested in touching upon briefly the issue of diplomatic relations between Georgia and the Republic of Malta.

➤ Diplomatic relations between Georgia and the Republic of Malta were established on 1 February 1993.

➤ Since 2004, the Republic of Malta's full range of consular services has been performed by the Embassy of Georgia in the Republic of Italy.

To conclude

Today, when Georgia has been awarded the status of a candidate state for the European Union, I think that a detailed study of the path of European countries' accession to the European Union and the exchange of knowledge in this direction is of great importance. Both government agencies, educational centers and universities should be involved in this process. It is necessary to create special programs and announce internal grant competitions.

For some reason, examples are not taken from the history and political experience of states about which Georgian society knows relatively less. Malta is a prime example of this. At this time, it should be recognized that Malta's path to the EU is no less interesting and important. It is worth noting the connection between the constitutional norms of Malta and issues related to European integration and current topics that the new Europe offers us. Our country's special interest in this EU country is determined by the following features:

- ✓ The role of religion in this small country
- ✓ cultural diversity of Maltese society,
- ✓ similarity with our constitutional norms,
- ✓ Strong sense of preserving European values,
- ✓ High tourism potential,
- ✓ Malta and UNESCO,
- ✓ Malta - sea connections, etc.

Therefore, in the process of Georgia's European integration, I consider it advisable to pay more attention to teaching law and politics about those states that our society is less informed about. Among these countries are EU members: Croatia, Slovenia, Malta. Since the Constitution of Georgia is going through a very complex and responsible path of development, it is extremely important to study the constitutional norms of these countries.

References

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5. Official Website of the Government of Malta: <https://www.gov.mt/mt/Pages/home.aspx>, You can also get acquainted with the text of the Maltese Constitution here.